

COMPARATIVE EXPOSURE ASSESSMENT OF ESBL-PRODUCING *ESCHERICHIA COLI* THROUGH SEAFOOD CONSUMPTION

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SUMMARY

Extended-Spectrum β -Lactamase (ESBL) producing *Escherichia coli* (EEC) are a significant public health concern. Although previous studies have calculated the exposure through meat consumption, the risk from seafood has not been quantified. A Quantitative Microbiological Risk Assessment (QMRA) model for meat was adapted to incorporate the complexities along the seafood chain. Total exposure of the Dutch population (EEC / year) was highest for raw salmon (48.1%) and smoked eel (43.9%). The top five seafood products (raw salmon, smoked eel, caviar / cod roe, smoked salmon and anchovies) all had a higher annual exposure estimate than any meat product. The high exposure by raw salmon is due partly to the current EU legislation which permits farmed salmon to be sold without prior freezing. With current antimicrobial usage remaining high in aquaculture industries, the results question whether the current legislation is adequate to mitigate against emerging microbiological hazards such as antimicrobial resistance.

INTRODUCTION

Extended-spectrum beta (β)-lactamases (ESBL) are plasmid-encoded enzymes found in *Enterobacteriaceae* which confer resistance to a variety of beta-lactam antibiotics (EFSA, 2011). ESBL-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* may cause a range of clinical infections in people from urinary tract infections (UTI) to more serious bloodstream infections (Pitout and Laupland, 2008). Current Dutch prevalence levels suggest that 3% of patients who attend their General Practitioner and 7% of hospitalised patients in intensive care units (ICU) have an infection associated with ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli* (EEC) (NethMap, 2019). EEC was the third most frequent cause of serious large scale antimicrobial resistant outbreaks in hospital settings in the Netherlands in 2018 (13%, 8 /59 outbreaks) (NethMap, 2019).

The majority of human EEC carriage is acquired from other humans with recent studies indicating that the attribution from the open population (defined as clinically healthy individuals who had not travelled to high-risk regions nor are engaged in farming activities) may be as high as 60.1% (Mughini-Gras et al., 2019). Nonetheless, reports of EEC carriage in animals and meat products, particularly poultry products, have been reported since 2000 (EFSA, 2011) with food consumption and preparation accounting for 18.9% of human cases in the Netherlands (Mughini-Gras et al., 2019).

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Exposure assessments combine the prevalences and concentrations in raw products with human consumption, storage and cooking habits in order to compare the relative impact of different products on human exposure. Models comparing the risk of exposure to EEC through meat consumption found that beef products (78%) contributed more to the exposure risk than chicken (18%), pork (4.5%), veal (0.1%) and lamb (<0.1%) products (Evers et al., 2017). Equivalent exposure assessments have not been performed for seafood products. However, there are many perceivable reasons why exposure to EEC through consumption of seafood products could be high, including the frequent raw consumption of seafood products, heavy use of antibiotics in aquaculture and extensive international trade in fish goods. Mughini-Gras et al., (2019) found that the consumption of seafood (6.6% attribution, 95% confidence interval 0.3-21.6%) may be responsible for more cases of EEC carriage than either chicken meat (4.5% attribution, 95% confidence interval 0.2-13.1%) or bovine meat (3.6% attribution, 95% confidence interval 0.1-12.5%) (Mughini-Gras et al., 2019). Moreover, the ESBL subtypes CTX-M-15, CTX-M-14 and CTX-M-27, which were strongly associated with human-to-human transmission, were also common in seafood products (Mughini-Gras et al., 2019). The risk from seafood consumption needs to be examined in order to ensure the safe supply of seafood products.

The aim of this project is to quantify the total annual EEC exposure to the Dutch population through seafood consumption. It will use a Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment (QMRA) model to capture complexities along the seafood chain from harvest to consumption.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Model description

The model used was based on a previous model comparing EEC exposure through consumption of meat products (Evers et al., 2017). The model was adapted to estimate the exposure of the Dutch population to EEC through consumption of seafood products (Fig.1) and performed in @Risk 6.2 (Palisade Corporation). “Exposure” referred to the number of microorganisms on a food product at the point of consumption, and did not accommodate any dose-response parameters which are less relevant to antimicrobial resistance carriage (Evers et al., 2017). Due to the high proportion of fish products consumed raw, and the likelihood of a high pathogenic load in these products, the model concentrated on products which were not cooked prior to consumption (Table 1). Note that these products may undergo a variety of pre-retail processing (including hot smoking) and still be classed as consumed raw if they are not formally cooked prior to consumption. The total number of raw products evaluated was 14 although products may account for more than one commercial item (for example, raw salmon may be sushi or poké bowls). Additional raw seafood products (such as oysters) were excluded if they were not consumed in the most recent food consumption survey. There are some cultural differences in the terminology of some fish products. Hereafter, the study refers to hot-smoked herring as a kipper, raw herring as a soused herring and cold-smoked herring as a bloater.

In order to accommodate for the significant international trade in seafood products, the model was adapted to incorporate the effect of transport from point of catch to importation into the Netherlands. Fish were assumed to go from a starting temperature at the point of catch, T_{catch} to a transit temperature, $T_{transit}$ within a specified harvest time, $t_{harvest}$. An exponential primary growth model plus the temperature-dependent part of the gamma model as secondary growth model were taken from Evers et al. (2017). The temperature trajectory was divided into 10 parts, i , assuming a linear decrease in temperature from T_{catch} to $T_{transit}$ within $t_{harvest}$ hours.

An EEC generation time at temperature increment, $t_{gen,i}$ was calculated (Eq. 1) to create an overall EEC growth multiplication factor, G , during harvest (Eq. 2).

$$t_{gen,i} = \frac{t_{gen.min}}{\left(\frac{(T_{catch} - (T_{catch} - T_{transit})(i/9)) - T_{min}}{T_{opt} - T_{min}}\right)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$G = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^{n=10} e^{\left(\frac{\ln 2}{t_{gen,i}}\right) * \frac{tharvest}{n}} \quad (2)$$

EEC growth and survival parameters, namely the minimum generation time, $t_{gen.min}$, minimum growth temperature T_{min} and optimum growth temperature, T_{opt} were as previously described (Evers et al. 2017, Table 2).

Table 1. Description of seafood products in model

Product	Fish	Fish type ^a	Storage profile ^a
Smoked kipper	Herring	2a	Perishable
Salted herring	Herring	2a	Direct consumption
Smoked eel	Eel	1a	Direct consumption
Steamed mackerel	Mackerel	2b	Perishable
Bloater	Herring	2a	Perishable
Smoked salmon	Salmon	1a	Perishable
Pickled herring	Herring	2a	Shelf-stable
Smoked halibut	Halibut	1a	Perishable
Smoked mackerel	Mackerel	2b	Perishable
Raw farmed salmon	Salmon	1a	Direct consumption
Anchovy	Anchovy	2b	Shelf-stable
Caviar / cod roe	Sturgeon	1a	Shelf-stable
Raw tuna	Tuna	2b	Direct consumption
Salmon pate	Salmon	1a	Perishable

^aFor further details on fish types and storage profiles, see main body of the text

Pre-retail processes, namely techniques designed to retain raw characteristics, cold smoking, hot smoking and pickling were modelled by applying a log reduction to the raw products.

Storage at the consumer's home was modelled as per Evers et al. (2017). Briefly, storage could occur at room temperature, in the refrigerator or in the freezer. Growth of microorganisms could occur if the storage temperature exceeded the EEC minimum growth temperature, T_{min} . EEC is limited to a maximum population density. Inactivation due to exceeding the maximum population density per product was described as an exponential

decrease with storage time for room and refrigerator and time-independent for the fraction stored in the freezer.

Fig.1. Overview of QMRA model used for the calculations including details for each stage.

Output was calculated at the population level. The number of microorganisms ingested per contaminated portion was calculated alongside the number of portions consumed in a year by the Dutch population and the fraction of contaminated portions at consumption. The total exposure was calculated in order to estimate the attribution from each seafood product.

Table 2. EEC growth and survival parameters

Parameter	Value
Minimum generation time (hours)	0.47
Optimum growth temperature (°C)	37.5
Minimum growth temperature (°C)	6
Maximum population density (CFU/g)	1.23E+05
Fraction survival room (day ⁻¹)	1
Fraction survival fridge (day ⁻¹)	1
Fraction survival freezer (total reduction)	0.1

Parameter values

Prevalence on raw fish product: The literature was searched for studies which described either the prevalence or concentration of EEC within fish products. Due to limitations in data availability, it was assumed that fish of similar geographical distributions and whether they were a farmed or wild caught species would share similarities in concentration and prevalence data. Therefore, fish were classed into one of four categories according to information from FishBase, a global database of fish species (Froese and Pauly, 2019, Table 3).

Table 3. Classification of fish types

Category	Description	Possible examples
1a	Farmed fish from primarily cold waters	Salmon, eel, sturgeon, halibut
1b	Farmed fish from warm water	Trout, pangasius, tilapia
2a	Wild caught fish from primarily cold waters	Herring
2b	Wild caught fish from warm water	Mackerel, anchovy, tuna, sardines

One example fish species was chosen per category and all fish types within that category were assumed to have the same prevalence. If more than one source of information was available, the study sampling fish at retail closest to the Netherlands was selected. The EEC prevalences were 3.6% for category 1a products (based on salmon in Spain; Vitas et al., 2018) and 9.5% for category 1b (based on tilapia in the Netherlands; Maran, 2018). Data from wild caught fish (categories 2a and 2b) were unavailable and so the prevalence values were assumed based on values from farmed fish in the same geographical region (1a and 1b respectively).

Concentration on raw fish product: There were very little data on EEC concentrations on raw seafood products. Therefore, for each of the fish categories (Table 3), the literature was searched to find studies reporting non-ESBL *E.coli* concentrations. Non-ESBL *E.coli*

concentrations from category 1a were estimated at 4.71 log CFU/g based on sushi in Italy (sushi products were assumed to be primarily produced from salmon; Muscolino et al., 2014), category 2a were estimated at 1.8 log CFU/g (based on herring in the Philippines; Gabriel and Alano-Budiao, 2015) and category 2b were estimated at 3.35 log CFU/g (based on sardines in Algeria; Dib et al., 2018). Note that no fish products consumed raw belonged to category 1b and so were not included in the analysis. Ryu et al., (2012) sampled 2,663 seafood products and found that 8.4% of *E. coli* isolates carried the ESBL-resistance gene, *bla_{TEM}*. Therefore EEC concentration data were estimated to be 3.63, 0.72 and 2.27 log CFU/g for category 1a, 2a and 2b respectively.

Growth and inactivation during harvest: The Fish and Fishery Products Hazards and Controls Guidance state that scrombotoxin-forming fish which are exposed to air or water temperatures $>28.3^{\circ}\text{C}$ should have an internal temperature of $\leq 4.4^{\circ}\text{C}$ within 6 hours post-death or within 9 hours if exposed to air or water temperatures $\leq 28.3^{\circ}\text{C}$ (FDA, 2011). Fish were assumed to go from a starting temperature at the point of catch, T_{catch} , to a transit temperature, $T_{transit}$, of 4.4°C within a specified harvest time, $t_{harvest}$, of 9 or 6 hours depending on whether they were within fish subcategory a (fish within colder oceans) or b (fish within warmer oceans) respectively. T_{catch} was assumed based on the average annual Atlantic Ocean temperatures within temperate regions (16.1°C) and tropical regions (28.1°C) respectively (Temperature, 2019).

Growth and inactivation during transit: A proportion of seafood products are transported fresh (assumed 4.4°C) and a proportion are transported frozen. The United Nation’s Comtrade database was searched to calculate the net weight (kg) of imported frozen or fresh whole fish into the Netherlands from 2016-2018 for each fish type (U.N., 2019). The proportions imported frozen were then calculated (Table 4). In fresh products, no additional growth was assumed during transport as $T_{transit} < T_{min}$ (Table 2). Frozen products had an assumed 1 log reduction in EEC concentration during transit due to the freezing process (Evers *et al.*, 2017).

Table 4. Average proportion of fish imported into the Netherlands frozen from 2016 to 2018 according to United Nation’s Comtrade database.

Fish	Proportion imported frozen
Salmon	0.51
Tuna	0.53
Eel	0.69
Halibut	0.83
Caviar	0.9
Anchovy	0.97
Herring	0.98
Mackerel	0.98

Concentration reduction due to pre-retail processing: Log reductions were applied to the EEC concentrations after transit depending on whether pre-retail processes had been applied. Five categories of preretail processes were considered important (Table 5). The detailed pre-

retail processes for each product were taken from the Fish and Fishery Products Hazards and Control Guidance (FDA, 2011).

The main effect for category 1 products was individual quick freezing (IQF) with extended storage or high hydrostatic pressure processing (FDA, 2011). Soused herring, and raw tuna must be frozen at a temperature of $\leq -20^{\circ}\text{C}$ for ≥ 24 hours to kill anisakiasis parasites according to Regulation 853/2004 (European Union, 2004b), 854/2004 (European Union, 2004a) and 2074/2005 (European Union, 2005). Farmed salmon is exempt from the EU legislation requiring raw products to be rapidly frozen (European Union, 2005; European Union, 2004a; European Union, 2004b). These products are clearly listed in the food consumption surveys as “salmon farmed raw” and therefore, were assumed to have a zero log reduction (category 5). Caviar/cod roe is also eaten raw.

Table 5. Pre-retail processes applied in model.

Pre-retail category	Description	Products	Log reduction	Reference
1. Products designed to retain raw characteristics	Individual quick freezing (IQF) with extended frozen storage	Soused herring, raw tuna	3.52	(FDA, 2015; FDA, 2011)
2. Cold smoked	Lightly brined then cold smoked at 32°C .	Smoked salmon, salmon pate, bloater	3	(NACMCF, 2008; Sabanadesan <i>et al.</i> , 2016)
3. Hot smoked	Smoked and heated to 62.8°C for 30 minutes then salted at 2.5-3.5% water phase salt.	Smoked mackerel, kipper, smoked eel, smoked halibut, steamed mackerel	6	(NACMCF, 2008; FDA, 2011)
4. Pickled	$\text{pH} \leq 5.0$	Anchovy, pickled herring	4	(Glass <i>et al.</i> , 1992; FDA, 2011)
5. No processing	-	Raw salmon, caviar/cod roe	0	(European Union, 2004a; European Union, 2004b; European Union, 2005)

Growth and inactivation during storage at the consumer’s home: Products were classed into three storage profiles depending on whether they were items intended for direct consumption, perishable or shelf stable. Each storage category had different proportions of products stored at room, refrigerator and freezer temperatures. The storage time at these temperatures was also category-dependent. Room temperature was assumed to have a mean temperature of 18°C (Evers *et al.*, 2017), refrigerator temperature was assumed to have a mean temperature of 4°C (NACMCF, 2008) and frozen storage was assumed to be time (and therefore temperature) independent (Evers *et al.*, 2017).

Category 1: Direct consumption In contrast to meat items, a larger portion of seafood products were considered likely to fall into a “direct consumption” category (e.g. soured herring, smoked eel, raw salmon and raw tuna, see Table 1). It was assumed that 50% of these products would be stored at room temperature and consumed within a mean of 3 hours and 50% stored in the refrigerator and consumed within a mean of 6 hours.

Category 2: Perishable products The proportions of portions stored at each temperature (9% room, 81% refrigerator, 10% freezer) was taken from a Dutch food consumption and handling survey using responses for smoked salmon (Chardon and Swart, 2016). Mean storage times in the refrigerator (79 hours) were taken from the mean value for smoked salmon (Chardon and Swart, 2016). Storage time at room temperature was taken as 1/5th of that in the refrigerator (Evers *et al.*, 2017).

Category 3: Shelf stable Values for the proportion of portions stored (19% room, 80% refrigerator, 1% freezer) and storage time (168 hours at room temperature, 149 hours in refrigerator) for shelf stable products were taken from Evers *et al.* (2017).

A maximum storage time of five times the mean has been used previously when modelling meat products (Chardon and Swart, 2016). However, it was assumed that the freshness of a product would be more important for fish products than for meat products. Therefore a maximum storage time of twice the mean was applied. This assumption was assessed during the scenario analysis.

Population level consumption: The latest Dutch National Food Consumption Survey from 2012 – 2016 was analysed (RIVM, 2019). These surveys included 4,313 respondents including children aged 1-18 years (n=2,235) and adults aged 19-79 years (n=2,078). Food intake data was collected by two diaries and/or two non-consecutive 24-hour dietary recalls. The frequency of consumption and quantity consumed per serving (g) was collected for all seafood products listed as being consumed raw.

Scenario analysis

A scenario analysis was performed on parameters deemed most uncertain to investigate the impact of this uncertainty on the model results. Namely temperature at point of catch, T_{catch} , is 5°C cooler (scenario 1), pre-retail processes are 10-fold less efficient (scenario 2), pre-retail processes are 10-fold more efficient (scenario 3) and maximum storage time at five-times mean (scenario 4).

RESULTS

Smoked salmon, soused herring and raw salmon were the top three consumed products in the Netherlands from 2012 – 2016 (Table 4). The fraction of contaminated portions was highest for all category 2b products (mackerel, anchovy and tuna) at 9.5%. Exposure per contaminated portion (number of EEC per portion) was highest for smoked eel, caviar / cod roe and raw salmon and lowest for steamed mackerel, kipper and pickled herring. Total exposure (number EEC per year) was highest for raw salmon (48.1%), smoked eel (43.9%) and caviar / cod roe (4.6%).

An exposure assessment along the seafood chain can be seen for individual fish species (rather than products) from contamination at the start (stage 1), at the point of importation (stage 2), after pre-retail processing (stage 3) and at the point of consumption (stage 4) (Fig. 2). Harvest and transportation processes have a minimal effect in reducing the microbiological contamination levels, by an average of 0.5%. Pre-retail processes decrease the EEC concentrations on average by 35.1%. The largest reduction occurs in mackerel products 61.7%, halibut products 56.6% and herring products 53.5%. Storage by the consumer increases the EEC contamination in all products, by an average of 12.4%. This effect is largest in anchovy (50.2%), halibut (21.4%) and sturgeon (12.5%) products.

Table 4. Contribution of different seafood products to the exposure of humans to EEC through seafood at the moment of consumption.

Product	Total number of portions consumed per year	Exposure per contaminated portion (EEC CFU/portion)	Total exposure (EEC CFU/year)	Total attribution (%)
Raw salmon	3.83E+07	1.52E+05	2.03E+11	48.1
Smoked eel	7.45E+06	1.02E+06	1.85E+11	43.9
Caviar / cod roe	1.35E+06	4.30E+05	1.93E+10	4.6
Smoked salmon	9.03E+07	3.73E+03	1.20E+10	2.8
Anchovy	2.71E+06	1.05E+05	1.60E+09	0.4
Salmon pate	2.71E+06	6.65E+03	6.40E+08	0.2
Raw tuna	1.35E+07	8.15E+01	9.92E+07	<0.1
Soused herring	3.99E+07	4.00E+00	2.26E+06	<0.1
Smoked halibut	6.77E+06	2.35E+01	1.80E+06	<0.1
Smoked mackerel	2.03E+07	2.50E+00	1.90E+05	<0.1
Bloater	6.77E+05	1.05E+01	8.99E+03	<0.1
Steamed mackerel	2.03E+06	5.00E-01	3.47E+03	<0.1
Kipper	2.71E+06	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	<0.1
Pickled herring	1.08E+07	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	<0.1

Results from the uncertainty analysis show that the effect of parameter values on the contribution from the five highest attributed products was generally limited (Fig. 3). However, the attribution to smoked eel was reduced in all uncertainty analysis scenarios. Moreover, when maximum storage times were five-times average times (scenario 4), pickled herring obtained 60% of the total attribution in that simulation (results not shown).

DISCUSSION

The model presented here is an adaptation of a previous exposure assessment for EEC through consumption of meat products (Evers *et al.*, 2017). It has been adapted to capture complexities along the seafood chain including the effect of harvest temperatures, probability of frozen produce at importation and pre-retail processes unique to seafood production. The two products with the highest EEC exposure (raw salmon and smoked eel) accounted for 92% of the exposure to the Dutch population. The three highest meat products for EEC exposure were filet americain (7.16E+8 EEC per year), chicken fillet (1.47E+8 EEC per year) and ossenworst sausage (1.01E+8 EEC per year) (Evers *et al.*, 2017). The top five seafood products (raw salmon, smoked eel, caviar / cod roe, smoked salmon and anchovies) all had a higher annual exposure estimate than any meat product. This is in agreement with a recent source attribution study, which predicted that consumption of seafood (6.6% attribution) could have a higher risk than consumption of chicken meat (4.5% attribution) or bovine meat (3.6% attribution) (Mughini-Gras *et al.*, 2019).

Fig. 2. ESBL-producing *E.coli* population-level exposure at each stage of the seafood chain (1 at catch, 2 at importation, 3 at retail, 4 at point of consumption).

Four out of the top five fish products (raw salmon, smoked eel, caviar / cod roe and smoked salmon) were categorised into group 1a which had the highest EEC concentrations at baseline. This class was categorised as “farmed fish from cold waters”. Antibiotic use in salmon aquaculture ranges from ~0.02-0.39 g/tonne harvested biomass in Scotland and Norway to ~660g/tonne in Chile (Rodriquez and Pastor, 2015). It is clear that seafood products have the potential to pose antimicrobial resistance (AMR) risks to public health (Watts *et al.*, 2017). Further work is needed to understand the risk of antimicrobial usage in aquaculture to human health.

Raw salmon (a product categorised as having no pre-retail processing) contributed 48.1% to EEC exposure by seafood whereas smoked salmon (a cold smoked product) had a contribution of only 2.8%. Farmed salmon is exempt from the EU legislation requiring raw products to be rapidly frozen (European Union, 2004a; European Union, 2004b; European Union, 2005). Conversely, raw tuna (ranked 7th in overall exposure) and soused herring (ranked 8th in overall exposure), both products intended to be consumed raw, must be frozen at a temperature of $\leq -20^{\circ}\text{C}$ for ≥ 24 hours to kill anisakiasis parasites. More research is needed to investigate whether emerging aquaculture hazards, like AMR, are adequately controlled by current EU legislation. Arguably, there should be a more risk-based approach to pre-retail processes, including the freezing of all farmed aquaculture products. The increasing popularity for consumption of raw salmon adds more weight to the need to thoroughly investigate the microbiological safety of this product.

Fig. 3. ESBP-producing *E. coli* attribution (%) from five highest seafood products according to the baseline model (scenario 0). Results from uncertainty analysis are shown (Scenario 1, temperature at point of catch, T_{catch} , is 5°C cooler; scenario 2, pre-retail processes are 10-fold less efficient; scenario 3, pre-retail processes are 10-fold more efficient; scenario 4, maximum storage time at five-times mean).

Caviar / cod roe and anchovy were the third and fifth highest ranking products for EEC exposure. These products were both classed as “shelf-stable” in the consumer stage. Storage at the consumer phase increased EEC contamination by 12.4% on average and up to 50.2% in anchovy products. The storage of food products by consumers was taken from a Dutch food consumption and handling survey (Chardon and Swart, 2016) as well as similar QMRA models (Evers *et al.*, 2017). These surveys are invaluable in understanding consumer habits and comparing the relative risks of different products. However, more research is needed to understand storage at a variety of food establishments including restaurants and fast-food establishments. This would enable a more reliable assessment of population-level exposure risks through routes other than those prepared by the consumer.

The data used in this study held several major uncertainties. EEC concentrations at the point of catch were based on one study reporting the prevalence of *bla*_{TEM} in *E. coli* samples from seafood products and several studies reporting *E. coli* concentrations from different geographical locations. Although the pre-retail processes were based on industry recommendations according to the Fish and Fishery Products Hazards and Control Guidance (FDA, 2011), it was not possible to establish how closely these processes were followed nor where regular breaks in the guidance occurred. Many of the log reductions after the pre-retail processes were based on bacteria other than *E. coli*. Fewer studies were available because *E. coli* is not typically considered as a key indicator of contamination in fish products, which are typically more concerned with *Vibrio* and *Listeria* spp. It should therefore be assumed that absolute exposure values in this study are very uncertain. However, relative exposures are likely to have less uncertainty and so this study is useful in understanding which seafood products to target for surveillance or intervention studies. More research is needed to understand the processes involved in the seafood chain, including for example, harvest and

transit practices, the maintenance of the cold-chain from harvest to retail and pre-retail processes, and their impact on *E.coli* (and EEC) concentrations. When compared to slaughterhouse practices and meat chain processes, seafood products and the fishing industry receive little research interest from Veterinary Public Health scientists. The General Food Law requires food legislation to be based on “risk analysis” (EFSA, 2005). The lack of research interest in seafood products is an area which deserves further attention in order to ensure that seafood products are adapting to emerging Public Health concerns.

This study highlighted that the risks of EEC exposure from seafood consumption are not inconsequential. Raw salmon, smoked eel and caviar / cod roe ranked top for EEC exposure. The model highlighted difficulties in understanding the complexity of the seafood industry and suggested areas where more research is needed.

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